

Model of Institutional Capacity Development of the Health Technology Assessment Committee: Study on the National Health Insurance Program in Indonesia

Sintha Utami¹, Bambang Supriyono², Budi Wiweko³, Suryadi⁴, Endah Setyowati⁴
^{1,2,4,5}Universitas Brawijaya, Malang Indonesia
³Universitas Indonesia, Depok, Indonesia
Email: sinthakurniawan27@gmail.com

Abstract

This study aims to describe and analyze the effective institutional capacity development of the Health Technology Assessment Committee, from now referred to as the KPTK, in implementing the National Health Insurance program, from now on referred to as JKN, and to find the ideal model for developing the institutional capacity of the KPTK in terms of organizational strengthening dimensions. This study uses a qualitative descriptive approach with a post-positivism research paradigm characterized by determinism, reductionism, empirical observation, and measurement accompanied by theoretical verification. The study results show that the institutional capacity development of the Health Technology Assessment Committee (KPTK) must pay attention to Collective Commitments, facilitative leadership, regulatory reform, and increasing its strengths and weaknesses. Meanwhile, from the organizational strengthening dimension, the institutional capacity development of the KPTK must include the organizational structure, work mechanism, organizational culture, budget system, and infrastructure. The suitable KPTK institutional development model consists of 6 points, namely 1) early stakeholder involvement, 2) needs and potential assessment, 3) organizational strengthening, 4) capacity building program development, 6) capacity building program implementation, and 6) outcome evaluation capacity building program.

Keywords: Capacity Development, Institutional, Health Technology Assessment Committee (KPTK), National Health Insurance (JKN).

DOI Number: 10.14704/NQ.2022.20.15.NQ88053

NeuroQuantology2022;20(15): 520-531

A. INTRODUCTION

The health sector's development of science and technology has progressed rapidly from year to year (Nyonator et al., 2005; Atkinson & Blanpied, 2008; Paim et al., 2011). Increased life expectancy, changes in lifestyle, and the high incidence of communicable and non-communicable diseases also have the potential to increase the consumption of health services and resources in the utilization of the Health Insurance Program (Boutayeb & Boutayeb, 2005; Mayosi et al., 2009; Muhsen

et al., 2017). The development of technology and health services has given rise to many new drugs, medical devices, and procedures, so it is necessary to conduct a health-based technology assessment to determine effective and efficient drugs/procedures (Gulacsi et al., 2002; Ciani et al., 2012; Altenstetter, 2017)

In Law Number 40 of 2004 concerning the National Social Security System, often known as SJSN, the government combines and synchronizes the social security system to ensure that residents may sufficiently meet

their fundamental necessities. SJSN is one of the government's initiatives to fulfill global commitments and the mission of the 58th World Health Assembly (WHA) decision from 2005. (Yustina, 2019). Every country should develop Universal Health Coverage (UHC) or universal health insurance for its full population, as determined by the meeting (O'Connell et al., 2014; Zaman & Hossain, 2017). The meeting also agreed on the need to develop a health financing system that ensures access to sustainable health financing for the entire community and ensures that every citizen has equitable access to promotive, preventative, curative, and rehabilitative health services of high quality at affordable prices (Guinto et al., 2015; Van Minh et al., 2014).

A Health Technology Assessment is required to ensure the long-term viability of the JKN's health services (Adiyanta, 2020). Health Technology Assessment (HTA) is a formal review of health technology used to inform policy decisions, including safety, efficacy (benefit), costs and cost-effectiveness, and implications for organizational, social, and ethical concerns (Drummond et al., 2008). Based on the classification, technology and health services include the type of technology used (drugs, vaccines, blood products, pacemakers, diagnostic tests); the purpose or benefits of using technology (preventive, promotive, screening, diagnostic, curative, rehabilitative, palliative); and utilization of future technology, technology in the experimental stage, technology in the evaluation stage, proven technology and ancient technology (Rindfleisch, 1997).

Health technology assessment (HTA) is a systematic evaluation of the characteristics and consequences of the distribution and usage of health technologies (Vis et al., 2020). It is widely helpful in improving the quality of health services, providing scientific evidence from research to overcome existing problems, or at least reducing the magnitude of the problem, conducting a comprehensive, systematic, and transparent study of all aspects of the use of

technology. After adjusting to local conditions, the study's results can be used to prepare or revise the Clinical Practice Guide (Goodman & Ahn, 1999). In simple terms, HTA is a means to evaluate the benefits of interventions, whether drugs, procedures, or technology, in terms of costs incurred and results obtained (Hettle et al., 2017). This helps decision-makers get the best possible combination and relevant results with the lowest possible cost within the available budget. HTA serves as a bridge between researchers and decision-makers (Andradas et al., 2008).

In Indonesia, the agency given the authority to carry out health technology assessments is the Health Technology Assessment Committee (KPTK). KPTK has been established for seven years since 2014 and is structurally an independent committee (Indonesia, 2017). In carrying out its main tasks and functions administratively and in terms of financing, the KPTK coordinates directly with the Center for Health Financing and Decentralization Policy.

Ideally, KPTK should be an independent organization and be outside the bureaucratic structure; in this case, all KPTK policies should not be affected by any situation or condition (Philips et al., 2004); this is one of the pillars of organizational strengthening based on the leadership aspect of KPTK, namely independence collegial that emphasizes the protection of individuals and society. This follows the view (CCOHTA, 2006) that an organization should have leadership pillars such as impartiality, relevance, coordination, quality, and stakeholder support. On the other hand, the central leadership aspect is the value of HTA studies that can provide the right direction in using technology in various factors. This value is obtained based on working, thinking, and broad scope (Thokala & Duenas, 2012). This value will be a milestone for the acceptance of the study's results by the entire health community (Sutarjo, 2006). Moreover, normatively, the KPTK still faces regulatory gaps or differences in provisions regarding the use of technology assessment (health

technology assessment) results between the Regulation of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia Number 51 of 2017 concerning guidelines for assessing health technology in the JKN program and the BPJS Health Regulation Number 1 of 2014 concerning the implementation of health social security.

According to Langaas et al. (2007), institutional capacity includes three main activities: namely: 1) skills improvement, 2) procedure improvement, and 3) organizational strengthening, on the other hand (Whittle et al., 2011) says that institutional capacity has a relationship which is very closely related to organizational effectiveness so that the institutional or organizational capacity development framework comprehensively consists of five levels of development, namely: 1) independence and legal framework; 2) organization and management; 3) human resources; 4) audit standards and methodology and lastly 5) communication and stakeholder management (Afrosai, 2015).

Milen (2001) defines institutional capacity as "the ability, skills, understanding, attitudes, values, relationships, behavior, motivation, resources, and conditions that enable each individual, organization, network/sector, and broader system to carry out their functions and achieve the development goals that have been set on a regular basis." The dimensions of institutional capacity are comprehensively put forward (Grindle, 1997), which consists of three dimensions: first, the dimension of human resource development, with a focus on aspects of professional personnel and technical capabilities covering training, hands-on practice, working climate conditions, and recruitment; second, the dimensions of organizational strengthening, focusing on aspects of management governance to improve the success of roles; and third, the dimensions of organizational strengthening, focusing on aspects of management governance to improve the success of roles.

In the context of this research, the development of the institutional capacity of

the KPTK is more focused on the aspect of organizational strengthening, as stated by (Grindle, 1997); this is following the practical problem that the institutional capacity of the KPTK is ordinary, but in terms of the work/tasks of the KPTK is extraordinary so that it is necessary to strengthen the KPTK institutions so that KPTK's main tasks and institutional functions are getting better, besides that KPTK is an organization that works collectively and focuses on organizational management governance to improve the success of the roles, main tasks, and functions of health technology assessment.

Referring to the various problem phenomena described above, it can be understood that organizational strengthening is an essential component of KPTK's institutional capacity development. However, it should be noted that the success rate of KPTK in the assessment of health technology is not only determined by the strengthening of the organization but also by the aspect of the effectiveness of the strengthening of the organization so that there is continuity between the dimensions of organizational strengthening and the level of effectiveness. This is as stated by Kibbe et al. (2004) that health and effectiveness in the context of organizational strengthening require consistent and continuous attention.

Referring to the background of the problems described above, the institutional capacity development of KPTK is reviewed based on the dimensions of ideal and effective organizational strengthening in the National Health Insurance (JKN) program; it is essential to study in depth supported by organizational effectiveness and the ideal model of KPTK which is reviewed based on dimensions of organizational strengthening.

B. METHOD

This research on the institutional capacity building of the Health Technology Assessment Committee in the National Health Insurance (JKN) program uses a qualitative descriptive research approach with a post-positivism research paradigm. In the post-

positivism paradigm, researchers will see the extent of the consistency between the perspective or paradigm to the chosen method. Various research paradigms explain what they want to do and what falls within and outside the boundaries of legitimate research (Denzin, 1978). This paradigm is characterized as research that is determinism, reductionism, empirical observation, and measurement, and accompanied by verification theory (Creswell, 1994).

This study employs an interactive data analysis methodology from (Miles et al., 2014), which is an analysis that is conducted continually throughout data collecting in the field until data collection is complete. This data analysis was chosen since this research involves multiple actions, including data analysis, data grouping, determining what is essential based on the research subject, and researching and deciding what to publish. Consequently, data analysis occurs concurrently or constantly with the study procedure. For instance, researchers collect data to compile documents and reports on the outcomes of KPTK's work, classify them, and then provide their descriptions in research reports. According to the study emphasis, this procedure is repeated for additional data collecting in order to address all research issues.

C. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Institutional Capacity Development

Studies on capacity building have spawned a variety of concepts and definitions. Some scientists define capacity building as capacity development or strengthening, which suggests an endeavor to develop current capacities. Others, however, refer to capacity construction as a creative process of generating capacities that do not yet exist (Ansari et al., 2012). Capacity building can be interpreted as an effort to strengthen the capacity of individuals, groups, or organizations, as evidenced by the development of abilities, skills, potential, and talents, as well as the mastery of competencies, so that individuals, groups, or organizations can survive and overcome the

challenges of rapid and unexpected change. (Eade, 2007).

It is common to use the term "capacity development" to describe operations that improve an organization so that it can carry out its mission more successfully (Backer, Thomas E.) (Light & Hubbard, 2004). According to Light & Hubbard, "capacity development focuses on enhancing the leadership, management, and/or operation of an organization—the skills and mechanisms that allow a nonprofit to articulate its mission, gather and manage relevant resources, and ultimately achieve the outcomes it desires" (Light & Hubbard, 2004). In the meantime, according to Merilee S. Grindle, "capacity building is meant to incorporate a range of measures for enhancing the efficiency, effectiveness, and responsiveness of government performance" (Grindle, 1997).

Capacity Building is focused on: (1) the ability of the workforce (labor), (2) the ability of technology in the form of an organization or institution; and (3) "capital" capabilities such as resources, facilities, and infrastructure. In general terms, capacity building can be interpreted as building the capacity of individuals, groups, or organizations (Fiszbein, 1997).

Institutional is defined as the rules of the game, norms, prohibitions, policy contracts, and laws and regulations that regulate and control the behavior of individuals in society or organizations to reduce uncertainty in controlling their environment and inhibit the emergence of opportunistic and mutually detrimental behavior so that human behavior maximizes welfare. Individuals are more predictable (Edquist & Johnson, 1996). Differences between institutions and organizations are still considered biased. Organizations that have gained a remarkable position and legitimacy in the community because of their success in meeting the needs and expectations of the community for a long time can be said to be "institutionalized" (Spiller & Tommasi, 2008). With these several opinions, the author believes that the institution is an

order that has relationships between community members or interrelated organizations in an organization that is emphasized norms, codes of ethics, and formal and informal rules that work together to achieve goals.

Institutional capacity building/organizational development is a crucial and decisive aspect of bureaucratic change. It motivates attempts to achieve a government that fits the standards for good governance (Gunnarsson, 2001). According to Hilderbrand and Grindle, "organization capacity development refers to the structure, processes, and resources of organizational theories and management styles that members of the organization should implement" in the context of developing the capacity of public organizations (government) (Hilderbrand & Grindle, 1997).

Hilderbrand and Grindle (1997) describe three organizational development levels: "Capacity at an organizational level is determined by the performance and culture of the organization, which influence the development of resources. At the individual level, capacity identification focuses on local human resource management, such as the recruitment system, and the effectiveness of

training to raise the personnel knowledge, skills, and competencies of local public officials in the creation of sound plans and budgets. The system capacity operates within a regulatory or policy framework. This level is addressed in support of national policy and regulation to ensure the development of human resources (individual aspect) and organizational performance in order to build a sound plan and budget. The inconducive state at the system level will restrict the ability of bureaucracy to work well".

In addition, Hilderbrand and Grindle (1997) note that "the capacity of an institution is affected by the objective, the task, how authority is defined, and how incentives are provided" as sources of organizational theory, as well as the management style that members of the organization are required to employ. According to this theory, institutional capacity is influenced by objectives, the assignment of tasks, the definition of authority, and the distribution of incentives. It must be balanced in every respect.

The following is a comparison matrix of the capacity development of public organizations collected from various theories:

Table 1 Capacity Development of Public Organizations

Level	Grindle & Hilderbrand	Grindle	Franks	Focus Capacity building
Individual	Labor	Training and specific skills Procurement or provision of professional personnel Recruit and retain competent staff Pay attention to an adequate compensation structure	Knowledge, skills of individual attitudes Expanding skills, increasing knowledge, transferring skills, and improving attitude	
Organization	Organizational structure, processes, resources, and	Microstructure to improve performance, specific tasks, and	Development of managerial system capacity, improvement,	Organizational capacity building

	management style of the organization The main tasks and functions of the organizational unit that complete the task	functions through the arrangement of incentive systems, utilization of existing personnel, leadership, and communication of organizational structures.	and administrative procedures	
System	Economic, environmental activities, Organizational and social strategies	Macrostructure, changes to the rules of the game, mechanisms, accountability, system regulatory framework	Institutional development is the creation of a supportive environment with a legal and policy framework	Institutional reform

Traditional approaches to capacity building and organizational strengthening tend to place a disproportionate amount of emphasis on human resource management and related processes and structures. The new method takes a holistic view, taking into account not just internal factors but external ones as well (interactions with other entities, shareholders, and customers, as well as the system as a whole) (Milen, 2004). The aforementioned theory reveals that the expansion of an institution's capabilities is a contentious topic. Organizational strength can be improved in the following areas: strategy; culture; management; structure; human resources; finance; information assets; and infrastructure.

Several factors, including those listed below, affect capacity growth in the following ways:

- a) Collective Commitments. Capacity building takes a long time and requires a long-term commitment from all parties involved. In building an organization's capacity, both in the public and private sectors, Collective Commitments are the essential capital that must be continuously developed and maintained correctly. This commitment is not only for those in power but includes all components within the organization. The

influence of joint commitment is considerable because this factor forms the basis of all activities designed and goals to be achieved together.

- b) Conducive Leadership. Dynamic leadership opens vast opportunities for every element of the organization to carry out capacity building. A facilitative leadership like this will be a trigger tool for each element in developing its capacity.
- c) Regulatory Reform. Within an organization, regulations supporting capacity-building must be consistently drawn up and implemented. Of course, regulations are directly related to the smoothness of capacity building itself, for example, regulations for the existence of a reward and punishment system.
- d) Institutional Reform. In essence, it refers to the structural and cultural parts. The point is that a work culture supports capacity building. These two aspects must be managed in a way that becomes essential and conducive to supporting the capacity development program. For example, creating a good working relationship between employees and other employees or their superiors.
- e) Improved Strengths and Weaknesses. Identify strengths and weaknesses so

that an excellent capacity-building program can be arranged with the recognition of personal and institutional weaknesses and strengths of the available capacity. Then the weaknesses possessed by an organization can be quickly corrected, and the strengths of the organization are maintained and maintained.

2) K PTK Institutional Capacity in implementing the JKN program

Health Technology Assessment / HTA is a policy input consisting of a structured review of health technology and related concerns. It consists of safety, effectiveness (benefit), costs and cost-effectiveness, organizational consequences, and social and ethical concerns. Presidential Regulation No. 12 of 2013 article 43 paragraph (1) mandates HTA in JKN: "In order to ensure quality and cost control, the Minister is responsible for Health Technology Assessment, clinical advisory, and Health Insurance Benefits., Calculation of standard tariffs, Monitoring, and evaluation of the implementation of Health Insurance services."

The HTA Committee was established in accordance with the Decree of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia No. 171/Menkes/SK/IV/2014 regarding the Health Technology Assessment Committee and has been revised in accordance with Kepmenkes No. HK.02.02/MENKES/422/2016 regarding the Health Technology Assessment Committee. Any health technology that has not been guaranteed by the Health Insurance or has been guaranteed by the National Health Insurance but is deemed ineffective in terms of benefits and costs must be evaluated by the HTA Committee. Aspects of Health Technology Assessment include security, efficacy, effectiveness, economic factors, social, ethical, legal, political, and religious factors, egalitarian equity, affordability, and budget impact analysis (BIA).

Meanwhile, in developing the institutional capacity of the KPTK in implementing the JKN program in terms of

organizational strengthening dimensions, it includes:

a) Organizational structure

One way to strengthen an organization, according to the theory of organizational dimensions in capacity building (Milen, 2004), is to pay close attention to its internal processes and structures, which can have a significant impact on how it prioritizes its goals and arranges its daily operations. So at the institution, there is a need for an adequate organizational structure. Decree of the Minister of Health (Kepmenkes) RI Number 171/Menkes/SK/IV/2014, as amended by Decree of the Minister of Health No. HK.01.07/MENKES/249/2017 and Decree of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia No. HK.01.07/Menkes/6192/2020, states that the KPTK's current organizational structure is adequate. The Health Technology Assessment Committee's (KPTK) primary responsibilities fall into one of several categories, and each category has its own set of responsibilities (KPTK). This conforms to the fundamentals of an organization's structure theory (Rivai & Mulyadi, 2009), which highlights factors like job specialization and departmentalization as crucial in developing an effective structure.

b) Work mechanism

An organization possesses a mechanism that is operational and capable of realizing excellent governance by following what is aspired collectively in the process of performing tasks to reach common goals. Internal functions can only be operationalized and expedited with assistance from the outside, and this assistance must come in the form of working mechanisms with a variety of parties involved in the process of establishing institutional capacity.

The development of work mechanisms or working relationships carried out by the KPTK are, among others:

1. Introduction to HTA, evidence-based medicine, how to do a critical assessment of systematic review, and introduction to economic evaluation for the CAR Committee technical staff.

2. Studyvisit to HITAP (Health Intervention and Technology Assessment Program) Thailand (HTA Agency in Thailand).
3. Attended the Regional seminar on using Health Intervention and Technology Assessment in Support of Universal Health Coverage in India June 4th – 6th, 2015.
4. Study Visit to NICE (The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence) in the UK.
5. The participation of Ministry of Health policymakers, CAR Committee members, and CAR Committee technical staff in the Prince Mahidol Award Conference (PMAC) in Thailand.
6. Participation in The 4th Scientific Conference Of The African Health Economics And Policy Association (AfHEA), the theme of the 2016 conference was The Sustainability Development Goals (SDGs).

c) Organizational culture

One of the factors of organizational strengthening that (Milen, 2004) emphasizes in relation to the development of institutional capacity is strategy and culture. The relationship between the two demonstrates the need for guidance on one aspect: the process of attaining practical goals by establishing an organizational culture system with strategies for leadership, communication, and value systems. The KPTK data analysis is used to construct an organizational culture that positively influences the execution of all work activities in pursuit of shared objectives.

Capacity Enhancement pertaining to organizational culture Institutional capacity development provides clear indicators for institutionalizing a productive and positive organizational work culture based on the nation's cultural values. According to research findings, the KPTK has created a value system that serves as the foundation of work ethics. It can take the shape of courtesy, hospitality, and communication that demonstrates the nation's noble character. Consequently, work motivation is increasing as a result of this participatory and democratic approach. By increasing the importance of staff discipline,

KPTK's institutional capacity will be maximized.

d) Budget/Value System

According to the premise that CAR obligations are influenced by a number of elements, one of those factors is the need for adequate and fair funds. KPTK's institutional capacity-building program necessitates a budget to support the implementation of all organizational activities. In accordance with the World Bank's philosophy, which emphasizes capacity building concentrate on the organizational environment that leads to financial and budgetary support for carrying out all operations and meeting all organizational needs. According to study conducted by the KPTK, the fiscal allocation supplied by the pure state budget is sufficient, although having fallen from 2020-2021.

e) Facilities and infrastructure

One of the variables that are thought to have an effect on HTA is pretty decent equipment, which can include things like office equipment, communication tools, transportation equipment, and so on. According to this idea. The KPTK will regularly create new infrastructure facilities since the company is aware of the significance of having adequate infrastructure to assist in making the work of its employees easier.

3) KPTK Institutional Capacity Development Model in implementing the JKN program

Evaluation of the implemented capacity development program needs to involve stakeholders to enable the actors of the institutional capacity development program at the KPTK to see what areas need additional training, what areas should be prioritized, and in what ways capacity development can be incorporated into the institutional strategy. It involves constant reassessment and expecting changes depending on the changing situation. It includes evaluative indicators to measure the effectiveness of the initiated program. Evaluation of capacity development promotes accountability. Measurement is based on changes in institutional performance.

In the implementation, not all stages of capacity development follow the general stages as having been applied by default. Capacity building is usually done simply by providing training, socialization, and technical guidance and is often not 'grounded,' so the values to be instilled are less pervasive and poorly understood. As a result, capacity-building programs are less effective. Accountability for implementing capacity-building programs is also relatively low because it is only based on budget accountability and ignores accountability for processes and results. As a result, the capacity development program has not resulted in the development of the institutional capacity of the KPTK in implementing the JKN program as expected.

The results of this study propose a proposition that the effectiveness of the KPTK's institutional capacity development program will increase if the capacity development process involves all stakeholders. In general, capacity development includes 5 (five) stages, namely: 1) early stakeholder engagement, 2) needs and potential assessment, 3) capacity building program development, 4) capacity building program implementation, and 5) capacity building program evaluation results. In this study, the authors modify the KPTK institutional capacity-building model in implementing the JKN program by adding organizational strengthening.

Figure 1 KPTK-JKN capacity building model

D. CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion above, it can be concluded that there has been an implementation of institutional capacity development carried out to improve the performance of the KPTK in terms of organizational strengthening so that the main tasks and institutional functions of the KPTK can run better because KPTK is an organization that works collectively and focuses on governance. Manage organizational management. Organizational capacity development refers to the structure,

processes, sources of organizational theory, and management style that members of the organization must carry out. In capacity building, in terms of the dimensions of organizational strengthening, it is necessary to pay attention to factors that include Collective Commitments, facilitative leadership, regulatory reform, and increasing strengths and weaknesses. The development of the institutional capacity of the KPTK in implementing the JKN program can run effectively if the strengthening of the organization includes a) an organizational

structure where the KPTK already has an adequate structure in carrying out its functions and duties in accordance with each field that has been described in the main tasks of the Health Technology Assessment Committee (KPTK); b) next is the development of work mechanisms and working relations through the introduction of HTA, attending international seminars and conducting study visits; c) organizational culture where the organizational culture used in the KPTK is always based on the noble values of the nation's culture; d) a budget/value system in which strengthening the institutional capacity of the KPTK in the implementation of JKN is fully supported from the government budget through the APBN; e) facilities and infrastructure that support KPTK activities can effectively strengthen the capacity of the KPTK in carrying out its functions and duties. In this study, the model of KPTK's institutional capacity development in implementing the JKN program includes 1) early stakeholder involvement, 2) needs and potential assessment, 3) organizational strengthening, 4) capacity building program development, 6) capacity building program implementation, and 6) evaluation results of capacity building programs.

REFERENCES

1. Adiyanta, F. S. (2020). Urgensi kebijakan jaminan kesehatan semesta (Universal Health Coverage) bagi penyelenggaraan pelayanan kesehatan masyarakat di masa pandemi Covid-19. *Administrative Law and Governance Journal*, 3(2), 272-299.
2. Afrosai. (2015). *Institutional Capacity Building Framework – ICBF*.
3. Altenstetter, C. (2017). *Medical devices: European Union policymaking and implementing health and patient safety in France*. Routledge.
4. Andradas, E., Blasco, J. A., Valentín, B., López-Pedraza, M. J., & Gracia, F. J. (2008). Defining products for a new health technology assessment agency in Madrid, Spain: a survey of decision-makers. *International Journal of Technology Assessment in Health Care*, 24(1), 60-69.
5. Ansari, S., Munir, K., & Gregg, T. (2012). Impact at the 'bottom of the pyramid': The role of social capital in capability development and community empowerment. *Journal of Management Studies*, 49(4), 813-842.
6. Atkinson, R. C., & Blanpied, W. A. (2008). Research Universities: Core of the US science and technology system. *Technology in Society*, 30(1), 30–48.
7. Boutayeb, A., & Boutayeb, S. (2005). The burden of non-communicable diseases in developing countries. *International journal for equity in health*, 4(1), 1–8.
8. CCOHTA. (2006). The Canadian Coordinating Office for Health Technology Assessment (CCOHTA). *Business Plan 2005-2006*.
9. Ciani, O., Tarricone, R., & Torbica, A. (2012). Diffusion and use of health technology assessment in policy making: what lessons for decentralized healthcare systems? *Health Policy*, 108(2-3), 194-202.
10. Creswell, J. W. (1994). *Research Design: Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*. Thousand Oaks: SAGE Publications.
11. Denzin, N. (1978). *The Research Act. A Theoretical Introduction In Sociological Methods*. McGraw-Hills.
12. Drummond, M. F., Schwartz, J. S., Jönsson, B., Luce, B. R., Neumann, P. J., Siebert, U., & Sullivan, S. D. (2008). Key principles for the improved conduct of health technology assessments for resource allocation decisions. *International journal of technology assessment in health care*, 24(3), 244–258.
13. Eade, D. (2007). Capacity building: who builds whose capacity? *Development in practice*, 17(4-5), pp. 630–639.
14. Edquist, C., & Johnson, B. (1996). *Institutions and organizations in systems of innovation*. Univ.
15. Fiszbein, A. (1997). The emergence of local capacity: Lessons from Colombia. *World Development*, 25(7), 1029–1043.

16. Goodman, C. S., & Ahn, R. (1999). Methodological approaches of health technology assessment. *International journal of medical informatics*, 56(1-3), pp. 97–105.
17. Grindle, M. S. (1997). *Getting Good Government: Capacity Building The Public Sector of Developing Countries*. Boston, MA: Harvard Institute For International Development.
18. Guinto, R. L. L. R., Curran, U. Z., Suphanchaimat, R., & Pocock, N. S. (2015). Universal health coverage in 'One ASEAN': are migrants included? *Global health action*, 8(1), 25749.
19. Gulácsi, L., Dávid, T., & Dozsa, C. (2002). Pricing and reimbursement of drugs and medical devices in Hungary. *The European Journal of Health Economics*, 3(4), 271-278.
20. Gunnarsson, C. (2001). *Capacity building, institutional crisis, and the issue of recurrent costs*. Expert Group on Development Issues.
21. Hettle, R., Corbett, M., Hinde, S., Hodgson, R., Jones-Diette, J., Woolacott, N., & Palmer, S. (2017). The assessment and appraisal of regenerative medicines and cell therapy products: an exploration of methods for review, economic evaluation, and appraisal. *Health technology assessment*, pp. 1–204.
22. Hilderbrand, M., & Grindle, M. (1997). Building sustainable capacity in the public sector: what can be done? *Getting good government capacity building in the public sectors of developing countries*.
23. Indonesia, R. (2017). *Undang-Undang Republik Indonesia Nomor 36 Tahun 2014 Tentang Tenaga Kesehatan*. Manuscript.
24. Kibbe, B. D., Enright, K. P., Lee, J. E., Culwell, A. C., Sonsini, L. S., Speirn, S. K., & Tuan, M. T. (2004). *Funding Effectiveness, Lesson in Building Non-Profit Capacity*. Jossey-Bass - A Wiley Imprint.
25. Langaas, M. D., Odeck, J., & Bjørvig, K. (2007, September). The concept of institutional capacity building and review of road sector projects. In *23rd Piarc World Road Congress Paris* (pp. 17-21).
26. Law Number 40 of 2004 concerning the National Social Security System.
27. Light, P. C., & Hubbard, E. T. (2004). The capacity building challenge: A research perspective. *Practice matters: The Improving philanthropy project*, 3-60.
28. Mayosi, B. M., Flisher, A. J., Lalloo, U. G., Sitas, F., Tollman, S. M., & Bradshaw, D. (2009). The burden of non-communicable diseases in South Africa. *The Lancet*, 374(9693), 934–947.
29. Milen, A. (2004). *Pegangan Dasar Pengembangan Kapasitas. Diterjemahkan secara bebas. Yogyakarta: Pondok Pustaka Jogja*.
30. Miles, M. B., Huberman, M. A., & Saldaña, J. (2014). *Qualitative Data Analysis A Methods Sourcebook*. In *Qualitative Data Analysis A Methods Sourcebook* (3rd ed.). SAGE Publications Inc.
31. Muhsen, K., Green, M. S., Soskolne, V., & Neumark, Y. (2017). Inequalities in non-communicable diseases between the major population groups in Israel: achievements and challenges. *The Lancet*, 389(10088), 2531-2541.
32. Neonatal, F. K., Awoonor-Williams, J. K., Phillips, J. F., Jones, T. C., & Miller, R. A. (2005). The Ghana community-based health planning and services initiative for scaling up service delivery innovation. *Health policy and planning*, 20(1), 25–34.
33. O'Connell, T., Ramanathan, K., & Chopra, M. (2014). What does universal health coverage mean? *The Lancet*, 383(9913), 277–279.
34. Paim, J., Travassos, C., Almeida, C., Bahia, L., & Macinko, J. (2011). The Brazilian health system: history, advances, and challenges. *The Lancet*, 377(9779), 1778-1797.
35. Philips, Z., Ginnelly, L., Sculpher, M., Claxton, K., Golder, S., Riemsma, R., ... & Glanville, J. (2004). Review of guidelines for good practice in decision-analytic modeling in health technology assessment. *Health technology assessment (Winchester, England)*, 8(36), iii-iv.

36. Regulation of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia Number 51 of 2017 concerning guidelines for assessing health technology in the JKN program.
37. Rindfleisch, T. C. (1997). Privacy, information technology, and health care. *Communications of the ACM*, 40(8), 92-100.
38. Rivai, V., & Mulyadi. (2009) *Kepemimpinan dan Perilaku Organisasi*. Jakarta: Rajawali Pers.
39. Spiller, P. T., & Tommasi, M. (2008). The institutions of regulation: An application to public utilities. In *Handbook of new institutional economics* (pp. 515-543). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
40. Sutarjo, H. U. S. (2006). Leadership Health Technology Assessment Menghadapi Perubahan. *Majalah Kedokteran Indonesia*, 56(2), 41-45.
41. Thokala, P., & Duenas, A. (2012). Multiple criteria decision analysis for health technology assessment. *Value in health*, 15(8), 1172-1181.
42. Van Minh, H., Pocock, N. S., Chaiyakunapruk, N., Chhorvann, C., Duc, H. A., Hanvoravongchai, P., ... & Sychareun, V. (2014). Progress toward universal health coverage in ASEAN. *Global health action*, 7(1), 25856.
43. Vis, C., Bührmann, L., Riper, H., & Ossebaard, H. C. (2020). Health technology assessment frameworks for eHealth: A systematic review. *International Journal of Technology Assessment in Health Care*, 36(3), 204-216.
44. Whittle, S. R., Colgan, A., & Rafferty, M. (2011). *What the Literature Tells Us About Impact*. The Centre for Effective Services, Dublin. <https://www.advance-he.ac.uk>
45. Yustina, E. W. (2019). The Right to Self-Determination in Health Services and the Mandated Health Insurance Program for Universal Health Coverage. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity, and Change*, 8(5), 325-337.
46. Zaman, S. B., & Hossain, N. (2017). Universal Health Coverage: A burning

need for developing countries. *Journal of Medical Research and Innovation*, 1(1), 18-20.

